

ANALYSIS OF DEFINITIONS OF LITOTES SUGGESTED BY SCHOLAR

Tulanova Ominabonu Ğulomjon qizi

Student at Andijan State university

Egamnazarova Durдона Shuhratillaevna

Associate professor at Andijan State university

Abstract: Nowadays, it is very important to use stylistic devices and differentiate them in both oral and written speech. The current article is dedicated to the analysis of definitions of litotes by different linguists. In this article the author tried to compare them in particular.

Key words: Language, stylistics, litotes, stylistic devices, definition, negation, double negation.

АНАЛИЗ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЙ ЛИТОТ, ПРЕДЛОЖЕННЫХ УЧЁНЫМИ

Аннотация: В настоящее время очень важно использовать стилистические приёмы и различать их как в устной, так и в письменной речи. Настоящая статья посвящена анализу определений литоты разными лингвистами. В этой статье автор попытался сравнивать их отдельно.

Ключевые слова: Язык, стилистика, литоты, стилистические приёмы, определение, отрицание, двойное отрицание.

LITOTAGA OLIMLAR TOMONIDAN BERILGAN TA`RIFLARNING TAHLILI

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi vaqtda og`zaki va yozma nutqda stilistik vositalardan foydalanish va ularni farqlash juda muhimdir. Ushbu maqola turli tilshunoslar tomonidan litotaga berilgan ta`riflarning tahliliga bag`ishlanadi. Ushbu maqolada muallif ularni alohida solishtirishga harakat qildi.

Kalit so`zlar: Til, stilistika, litotalar, stilistik vositalar, ta`rif, inkor qilish va ikkilamchi inkor.

Litotes have really significant role in stylistics, make the speech polite that shows the attitude of the speaker to the listener from cultural point of view. Their stylistic functions of giving ironic and humorous effect to the utterance, make the statement more expressive, attract every writer and the listener and understates, lessens the main aspect of the speech. This phenomenon increased our interest in litotes and their stylistic functions and influenced on choosing the theme of the

article. Many scholars analyzed litotes and tried to give clear definition for them, which we will analyze further.

Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines litotes as —understatement in which an affirmative is expressed by the negative of the contrary, in other words, litotes is affirmation expressed through double negation. The functioning of litotes depends of the factors which are considered to be pragmatic constituents of any text as a means of communication: participants of the communication, pragmatic intention, pragmatic content, pragmatic effect and pragmatic potential [3, p 51; 1, p 172]

A lot of modern scientists (T. van Dijk, M. Reisigl and R. Wodak, K. Knorr Cetina) underline that together with metaphor litotes is one of the most powerful means of persuasive communication. The use of litotic statements is an example of linguistic manipulation, when authors intentionally apply some kind of language means to subliminally achieve the desirable result. Such features of litotes as negation and disharmony make it possible to employ litotes in two extreme cases when litotic statements are marred by negative connotations to stress and criticize negative features and litotes are used to highlight positive characteristics.

Litotes is a figure of speech in which understatement is employed for rhetorical effect, principally via double negatives. For example, rather than saying that something is attractive (or even very attractive), one might merely say it is "not unattractive".

Litotes is a form of understatement, always deliberate and with the intention of emphasis. However, the interpretation of negation may depend on context, including cultural context. In speech, it may also depend on intonation and emphasis; for example, the phrase "not bad" can be said in such a way as to mean anything from "mediocre" to "excellent". It can be used to soften harsher expressions, similar to euphemism. The use of litotes is common in English, Russian, German, Dutch and French. They are features of Old English poetry and of the Icelandic sagas and are a means of much stoical restraint. The word litotes is derived from the Greek word litotes meaning "plain, small or meager". [2, p 134]

Rawson Hugh complained about overuse of the 'not un...' construction in his essay. For example: "My word...it shall not return unto me void," meaning "My word...will have meaning and be important"

For example: "I will multiply them, and they shall not be few; I will make them honored, and they shall not be small," meaning "they shall be very many" and "they shall be very great"

For example: "They do not profit this people at all," meaning "they lead these people astray"

Usually litotes presupposes double negation. One is through a negative particle (no, not) the other is through a word with negative meaning. Its function is to convey doubts of the speaker concerning the exact characteristics of the object or a feeling.

For example: It's not a bad thing - It's a good thing.

For example: He is no coward. He is a brave man.

For example: He was not without taste.

Rarely heard, but extensively used - that is litotes among the regular speakers of English language. Popularly a figure of speech, the word 'litotes' originated from the Greek word 'litotes' which means simple. Litotes is defined as “**an ironical understatement in which affirmative is expressed by the negation of the opposite**”. In this figure of speech, the usages are intentional, ironical and provide emphasis to the words. This is mainly done through double negatives. To put it in simple terms, in litotes, instead of saying that something is attractive, you say that it is not unattractive. In literary circles, plenty of poets as well as writers have used this concept to convey strange and vivid images. It changes the thought process and thereby beautifies and adorns the literary works. Most of the literary works describe litotes in such a way that the words described are not false, but do not come near a complete description of the action in question. Rather, they are presented in a passive tone and demand more careful attention from the reader. Even figurative language use litotes to convey messages in a clear and impressive manner. [4, p 215]

Litotes is a two-component structure in which two negations are joined to give a positive evaluation. Thus "not unkindly" actually means "kindly", though the positive effect is weakened and some lack of the speaker's confidence in his statement is implied. The first component of a litotes is always the negative particle "not", while the second, always negative in semantics, varies in form from a negatively affixed word (as above) to a negative phrase and to make it polite.

Litotes is especially expressive when the semantic center of the whole structure is stylistically or and emotionally colored, as in the case of the following occasional creations.

For example: "Her face was not unhandsome" or "Her face was not unpretty".

The function of litotes has much in common with that of understatement – both weaken the effect of the utterance. The uniqueness of litotes lies in its specific "double negative" structure and in its weakening only the positive evaluation.[5]

As a conclusion, I can compare litotes with various cultures, because they deliver us information about cultural life of other nations. Litotes also reflect an inner aspect of people consciousness. The main motivation of working the theme of this article is because that this phenomenon stimulates our curiosity in litotes and their stylistic functions. The research included very tremendous investigation that we discover a definition of litotes by different scholars. Litotes remain in the language, but they are

used as stylistic devices to express politeness through double negations. Litotes usually do not use exact or direct meaning of the aspect but it hides and supplies indirect meaning weakening the statement.

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